

Change in the Work Function of the Electrons In Steel after Exposure to a Pulsed Magnetic Field

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In this article, we present the results of a study of the influence of a high-frequency magnetic field on the change in the work function of an electron in carbon steel (0.45% C) after heat treatment, including normalization, quenching, and temper hardening. The electron work function is determined on metallographic sections. The electron work function undergoes the greatest changes after exposure to a magnetic field in normalized steel, as well as in quenched and tempered steel. After quenching, the work function of an electron in steel does not change significantly. The effect observed can be attributed to the alignment of the microrelief on the surface of the samples, which is formed during preparation of a metallographic section, under the influence of a magnetic field. This results in a reduction in the number of mesoscopic surface defects.

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1. Introduction

Numerous studies are devoted to the effect of a magnetic field on various materials. Notable change, observed in the properties of materials, including those with different magnetic properties, is the reason for our interest. The observed facts are intriguing, especially since they cannot be explained from the standpoint of “classical” materials science.

In most applied studies, the general obtained result is an increase in tribological performance. In [1], it is found that treatment with an alternating magnetic field has led to a decrease in the friction coefficient by 18% and wear

rate by 41%. Additionally, there is a decrease in surface roughness and wear scar width. An increase in Vickers microhardness and residual compressive stresses on the surface have also been observed. The use of transmission electron microscopy have revealed that the observed effects are linked to increased mobility and dislocation migration towards the surface. A magnetic field can improve material transfer, accelerate tribofilm formation, and reduce stress concentration in polyetheretherketone/Cu nanowire composites [2]. The observed changes in properties are often linked to alterations in residual stress levels [3–5] and the density and configuration of dislocations [6, 7]. The effect of changing the intensity of the interference lines of Fe coatings on Cr₁₂MoV substrates by multilayer laser cladding under the influence of an electromagnetic field is observed in

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[5, 8]. In [9], an increase in material properties is observed when a magnetic field is applied during various surface treatments, including nitriding and boriding.

We have obtained results on the effect of alternating magnetic fields on metal and polymer materials. It has been found that a pulsed magnetic field is an effective means of changing the surface microrelief. [10], changes on the surface of materials under the influence of magnetic fields are observed, including the healing of microscopic defects in gray cast iron, the change in the relative position of the phases of the polymer material, and the appearance of the bearing steel surface. Twinning in brass under the influence of a magnetic field is demonstrated in [11]. Electroplated coatings exhibit a change in the level of residual stresses (macro stresses) and an increase in the uniformity of the distribution of chromium at the substrate-chromium coating interface, as observed in [12]. Experimental studies are conducted to determine the effect of treatment with an amplitude-modulated high-frequency electromagnetic field on the dynamic mechanical and tribo-acoustic characteristics of friction composites with a thermosetting polymer matrix. These composites are intended for use in non-stationary friction units of brake devices and machine transmissions. Research has shown that treatment with an electromagnetic field primarily affects the tangent of the mechanical loss angle, dynamic instability of friction, and spectral characteristics of frictional noise components above 2 kHz [13].

To comprehend the mechanisms of how a magnetic field affects surface processes such as friction and wear, it is necessary to obtain information on the changes in morphology and properties of materials' surfaces in magnetic fields. The scientific literature and our findings demonstrate the prospects of this approach.

The aim of this study is to change the work function parameters of electrons in steel 45 after exposure to a high-frequency magnetic field.

The electron work function (EWF) is a fundamental characteristic of a solid's surface

that determines its emission, contact, and adsorption properties [14]. The phenomenon of the EWF is that the forces of interaction with the crystal lattice prevent the electron exit from the metal, creating a surface potential barrier. Only electrons with sufficient energy can overcome these forces and leave the metal.

Even at absolute zero temperature, electrons in a metal possess energy, which is referred to as the Fermi level.

Therefore, to remove an electron from a metal, an energy equal to the difference between the surface potential barrier and the Fermi level of the metal must be given. This energy is called the work function of an electron from a metal.

The work function value of electrons in a crystalline solid is not constant and can change due to various factors. During mechanical compression or stretching, a change in the compactness of the metal lattice occurs, i.e., the volume of the crystal lattice changes, and, consequently, the volume occupied by free electrons. This shift causes a change in the position of the Fermi level and, consequently, a change in the work function of the electrons.

Defects in the metal crystal lattice have a significant effect on the EWF. Specifically, linear defects such as edge and screw dislocations have a particularly large impact on the work function [15].

Overall, there is no doubt that the work function of an electron is determined to the greatest extent by the structure and composition of the surface of a solid. In [14], data are given on the dependence of EWF on various factors:

- Miller crystallographic indices (hkl) of the studied surface;
- the anisotropy of the composition of adsorption films and the degree of surface coverage by foreign atoms;
- crystal imperfections arising in the process of its growth or from technological impact, such as deformations, dislocations, point defects, and their complexes.

Particular attention is paid to inhomogeneities of the nanometer scale level.

Characterizing the properties of a metal surface using EWF is challenging due to its relationship with multiple physical and physicochemical parameters of the surface. This makes interpreting measurement results difficult [16]. To date, a number of studies have been carried out to establish the nature of such a relationship for individual mechanical parameters, and in most cases, the dependencies given in the scientific literature, due to the complexity of complete mathematical modeling that takes into account all influencing factors, are partially or completely empirical in nature. Thus, mathematical modeling of the EWF, ϕ , of a metal with a cubic crystal lattice, performed in [17], shows the presence of a power-law dependence of the form $E = \alpha\phi^6$ between the ϕ and the Young's modulus E of the metal. The results of experimental studies given by the same authors [18] confirm the existence of such a dependence, up to the constant α , depending on the type of crystal lattice, for all the studied metals. However, it is important to note that these works only consider defect-free metals and do not take into account the different orientations of crystal grains in a polycrystal or the effect of grain boundaries. This could be one of the main reasons for the discrepancy between the theoretical and experimental data in these studies.

The relationship between the EWF and the Vickers hardness (HV) values of the surface of metals and alloys is of considerable interest. In [19], a mathematical model has been developed to describe the relationship between the parameter HV and the EWF values, which also predicts the presence of a power dependence of the sixth degree of the form $HV = \beta\phi^6$ for this parameter. The results of experimental studies given in this work for alloys of the Cu-Ni system are in good agreement with this model. At the same time, the authors emphasize the strong influence of dislocations and other defects, as well as adsorbed substances present on the metal surface, up to individual adsorbed atoms, on

the results of EWF measurements. To eliminate the influence of these factors, these studies have been carried out on a defect-free surface microsection under high vacuum conditions after its thorough cleaning with an argon ion beam. The applicability of the model to the case of a non-ideal (containing defects and contamination) surface requires verification based on the results of independent studies, including those presented in this paper.

The purpose of this work is to assess the surface condition of carbon steel based on determining the EWF after exposure to a high-frequency magnetic field.

2. Materials and research methods

The study have been carried out on samples of carbon steel with 0.45% carbon content. The pre-treatment has involved normalization at 810°C, water quenching from 860°C, quenching and tempering at 450°C (see Table 1). The hardness after heat treatment have been controlled by the Rockwell method.

On heat-treated samples, metallographic sections have been made according to the generally accepted method. The microstructure of steel before and after exposure to a magnetic field has been analyzed on a metallographic complex based on a MICRO-200 microscope. The chemical etching of the surface for the examination of its microstructure has been executed by means of a 3% solution of nitric acid in ethyl alcohol. The method of targeted metallography have been used, in which the same section of the structure was photographed before and after magnetic exposure.

After that, high-frequency magnetic-pulse processing has been carried out on an experimental setup created on the basis of an alternating current generator VCHI-62-5-IG-101. The installation makes it possible to excite an electromagnetic field at an industrial frequency $f = 5.28$ MHz, localized in a water-cooled three-turn inductor with a length $L = 90$ mm

and an internal diameter $D = 80$ mm, which is connected as an inductive load to the output of the generator (Fig. 1). Samples 1 have been placed in a dielectric matrix “2” and introduced into the axial zone of the inductor “3” at a distance of 40 mm from its upper cut.

FIG. 1. Layout of samples in the inductor: 1 is the sample, 2 is the dielectric matrix for the sample position fixation, and 3 is the water-cooled inductor.

The root-mean-square values of the strengths of the magnetic H and electric E components of the electromagnetic field on the axis of the inductor are amounted to 590 A/m ($B \approx 1 \mu\text{T}$, with an error of $\sim 6\%$) and 12700 V/m (with an error of $\sim 4\%$), respectively. Amplitude values $H^* = \sqrt{2}H$ and $E^* = \sqrt{2}E$ and reaches 835 A/m ($B \approx 1.5 \mu\text{T}$) and 17960 V/m, respectively. The error in reproducing the operating mode of the generator have not exceed 0.5%, as a result of which the total error in determining the magnitude of the strength of the electromagnetic field acting on the sample is no more than 10%. The processing is done in air at atmospheric pressure, as shown in the cyclogram in Fig. 2. Each sample have been exposed to a high frequency sinusoidal magnetic

field modulated in amplitude from 0 to 835 A/m. The modulation period is $\Delta t \sim 3$ s and forms a single processing cycle. The number of unit cycles $n = 2$. In this case, the heating of the sample have not exceed 40–60°C, and thus the possibility of a thermal change in its structure is excluded.

FIG. 2. The single processing cycle of a high-frequency electromagnetic field [20].

By definition, ϕ is equal to the following expression:

$$\phi = E_{vac} - E_F,$$

where E_{vac} is the energy of an electron in vacuum outside the surface of a solid body, E_F is the Fermi level of the surface. The EWF have been measured by the scanning Kelvin probe (SKP) method for surface control [16]. When using this method, the relative value, RWE , of EWF is directly determined through the so-called contact potential difference U_{CPD} . Since the U_{CPD} is proportional to the difference in the Fermi levels of the investigated surface E_{F1} and the sensitive element E_{F2} located oppositely, the RWE is calculated as

$$RWE = \phi_2 - \phi_1 = (E_{vac} - E_{F2}) - (E_{vac} - E_{F1})$$

$$= E_{F1} - E_{F2} = eU_{CDP}$$

where e is the electron charge.

As you can see, the contact potential difference reflects the difference in the EWF of the electrometric probe and the surface area located opposite the probe. The classical SKP method used in this study implements measurements of the contact potential difference using the Kelvin-Zisman method, which is related to compensation measurement methods. According to this method, the contact potential difference determined by the Fermi level difference is reduced to zero due to the operation of a compensating voltage source included in the electric circuit between the electrometric probe and the sample, controlled by the mismatch signal generated in the process of modulating the probe-sample gap [21]. Since there is no real electron escape from the sample surface using this method, the measurements are completely non-destructive and do not affect the surface in any way. Considering that the Fermi level is defined as the mathematical expectation of the energy of electrons in the surface layer of a material, measurements using the Kelvin-Zisman method are characterized by averaging the values of the contact potential difference (and, accordingly, the EWF) over the entire surface area of the sample located opposite the electrometric probe. For macroscopic (significantly larger than the size of dislocations) probe dimensions, this makes it possible, to a certain extent, to level the influence of microscopic defects, grain boundaries, etc., on the measurement results [22]. On the other hand, when measuring in the scanning mode, this makes it possible to draw up a map of the distribution of relative values of the EWF of the surface, reflecting the heterogeneity of the distribution of the physical properties of the surface and to identify areas of concentration of metal defects, since the average values of the EWF in the control region depend on the fraction occupied in it defects, i.e. on their concentration under the electrometric probe. In this study, we have used a scanning electrometric probe with a sensitive element area of 0.8 mm^2 . The X and Y

coordinates of the rendered images are given in relative units, determined by the features of the software used, on a scale of 20 units/mm. Contact potential difference have been determined on thin sections after metallographic etching before and after exposure to a pulsed magnetic field.

3. Research results and discussion

The structure of steel after heat treatment is as follows: normalization – ferrite and perlite (Fig. 3); water quenching – martensite; temper hardening – secondary sorbite. The hardness is in accordance with the resulting microstructure.

The microstructure of the samples after magnetic treatment does not change significantly. In particular, Figure 3 shows the results of spot metallography of the sample after normalization and subsequent magnetic treatment. After processing by a magnetic field, the sharpness is somewhat equalized along the image field, and the ratio of individual elements of the structure and the morphology of the lamellar perlite grain in the center of the frame change. However, such changes are on the verge of sensitivity of the method [10]. Changes in the microstructure of samples with preliminary water quenching, as well as quenching and tempering, are not visually distinguishable at $1500\times$ magnification.

Figures 4–6 show the color maps of the distribution of the contact potential difference of the samples after heat treatment and exposure to a pulsed magnetic field.

The application of a magnetic field has the most significant impact on the alteration of the contact potential difference of a normalized sample and a temper hardened sample. However, the changes caused by the magnetic field on a water-quenched sample are insignificant.

Histograms of the distribution of the contact potential difference before and after treatment with a magnetic field are presented in Figure 7. After normalization, the samples show a clear shift in the distribution center from 40 mV to 25 mV after treatment. This indicates an increase

FIG. 3. (Color online) Steel microstructure: normalization (a), normalization and exposure to a magnetic field (b); the magnification is 1500 times the original size.

FIG. 4. (Color online) Distribution map of the contact potential difference: normalization (a), normalization and treatment with a magnetic field (b).

FIG. 5. (Color online) Distribution map of the contact potential difference: water quenching (a), water quenching and treatment with a magnetic field (b).

FIG. 6. (Color online) Distribution map of the contact potential difference: temper hardening (a), temper hardening and magnetic field treatment (b).

FIG. 7. (Color online) Histograms of the distribution of contact potential difference: normalization (a), water quenching (b), temper hardening (c); blue — before treatment with a magnetic field, red — after treatment with a magnetic field.

Table 1: Pre-heat treatment modes, hardness and contact potential difference of samples

No.	Heat treatment mode	Hardness, HRC	Contact potential difference before magnetic field treatment, μV	Contact potential difference after magnetic field treatment, μV
1	Normalization	10	40	25
2	Water quenching from 860°C	55	25	30
3	Water quenching from 860°C, tempering 450°C 2 h.	33	40	19

in the electron work function (which has an opposite sign to the contact potential difference) of 15 mV. The center of the distribution of contact potential difference values for samples made of water-hardened steel is at a value of 25-30 mV. In contrast to previous cases, the application of magnetic treatment did not result in a significant shift in the electron work function values. However, the histogram of the distribution of the results became wider, which indicates an increase in the degree of surface heterogeneity. For the temper hardening sample, the same trend as for the normalized sample is repeated: magnetic field treatment reduced the contact potential difference to approximately 19 mV. The shape of the histograms varies significantly. Thus, if the distribution for normalized samples is close to Gaussian, the decline in the histogram towards higher values of the contact potential difference is much sharper than towards lower values for temper hardening samples.

For samples after magnetic treatment, the effect of bifurcation of the histogram peak is observed, possibly also due to the division of the surface of the treated samples into unetched and etched areas.

In general, the results of measurements of the spatial distribution of the contact potential difference suggest that magnetic treatment significantly affects the surface properties of normalized and temper hardened samples, but little changes the surface properties of water quenched steel.

The concepts developed in [24] can be used to explain the observed changes in the contact

potential difference. It is known that EWF is determined by the sum of volume and surface components. The volume fraction of the EWF depends on the Fermi energy of the given metal and changes very little upon deformation. The surface component of the EWF can undergo significant changes under deformation, since it is determined by local surface potential jumps, the variations of which depend on the microgeometry and coordination of surface atoms. It has been demonstrated that deformation processes on the surface are determined by the formation and evolution of nanometric defects. These are nanometric defects in the form of prisms of various sizes, the walls of which are formed due to the emergence of dislocations on the surface along easy slip planes. The formation of dislocation steps on the surface changes the electrostatic surface barrier and, accordingly, the work function of electrons. In [24], a method has been developed for calculating changes in EWF during elastoplastic deformation of metals based on a model of the relationship between EWF and the electronegativity of metals, taking into account the formation of nanometric surface defects.

It is possible that the increase in EWF observed in [24] is associated with a change in the nature of surface deformation during fine grinding and an increase in the concentration of large nanometric defects.

As a result of exposure to magnetic field, a decrease in the contact potential difference of the samples in the normalized and temper hardening states is observed. The observed effect should be associated with the leveling of the surface

FIG. 8. (Color online) Structure of the surface of the electroplated chromium coating in the initial state (a) and after treatment with a magnetic field (b); bright-field illumination [23].

relief under the action of a pulsed magnetic field. During the preparation of a metallographic section, the surface becomes a friction surface with a relief a few microns deep. The relief will be minimal for water quenched specimens and slightly larger after normalization and temper hardening.

The modification of the surface is one of the effects noted during magnetic pulse treatment [23]. This has been demonstrated specifically for electroplated chromium coatings (see Figure 8). In the initial state, the surface of crystallites formed during the galvanic process is convex (see 8a). Such a conclusion can be drawn, in particular, based on the illumination of various parts of the surface. The central part of the crystals is brightly lit. Their edges adjacent to the borders are darkened. Considering the conditions for the formation of a bright-field image in a metallographic microscope, such effects are observed if the surface of the object is uneven. Areas perpendicular to the central rays incident from the lens are brightly illuminated, sloping areas are darkened. After exposure to a pulsed magnetic field, the pattern of illumination distribution over the surface changes (see 8b). The surface is smoothed, and the zones of reduced illumination near the boundaries of the crystals disappear or are significantly narrowed. Impurity inclusions are noticeable within the boundaries,

probably formed during the formation of the coating. After high-frequency magnetic-pulse processing, the boundaries of the crystals lose their clear outlines and the crystallites no longer have the form of clear polygons, but instead resemble the grain structure of metal alloys. These changes in the surface of the coating significantly affect its wear resistance. Similar changes in the surface after magnetic-pulse processing have been also observed in [10, 20].

4. Conclusion

This study is carried out to determine how a high frequency magnetic field affects changes in an electron's work function in carbon steel with 0.45% carbon content after different heat treatments, including normalization, water quenching, temper hardening.

The largest changes are observed in EWF after exposure to a magnetic field for steel in its initially normalized state, as well as for temper hardened steel. However, the change in EWF is not significant for the steel after water quenching.

The observed effect can be explained by the alignment of the microrelief of the surface of the samples formed during the preparation of a metallographic section under the influence of a magnetic field and, thereby, a decrease in the

number of mesoscopic surface defects.

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